

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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THE PALACES OF THE BUKHARA EMIR.

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Annotation . This in the article Bukhara of the emirs their palaces is located instead of Initially In Kogon the palace Bukhara of the city inside construction in the eye but that of Bukhara to the eye appeared religious scholars to this strictly resistance they showed about , of this the reason is religious scholars strangers To Bukhara entrances obstruction they do From this after the palace 12 km east of Bukhara in the section " New Bukhara ", later Call it Kogon started in the town construction about the only one stop that they agreed about data statement done.

Key words : Amir, Kogon Palace , Mauritania in the style of baroque1, empiric and Arabic methods , Benoit .

BUXORO AMIRI SARAYLARI.

Annotatsiya. Bu maqolada Buxoro amirlarining saroylari o'rniga dastlab Kogonda saroy Buxoro shahar ichidagi qurilish ko'zda, Buxoroniki ko'z o'ngida diniy ulamolar paydo bo'lgan, ular bu borada qattiq qarshilik ko'rsatganlar, shu sababli. din ulamolari musofirlardir Buxoroga kirish yo'llarida to'siqlar qiladilar Bundan saroydan keyin Buxorodan 12 km sharqda "Yangi Buxoro" bo'limida, keyinchalik uni Kogon deb ataydigan shaharchada birgina bekat to'g'risida qurilish boshlangan, ular ma'lumotlar bayonnomasi bajarilgani haqida kelishib olishgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Amir, Kogon saroyi, barokko uslubida Mavritaniya1, empirik va arabcha uslublar, Benua.

ДВОРЦЫ БУХАРСКОГО ЭМИРА.

Аннотация. Это в статье Бухара эмиров, их дворцы расположены вместо Первоначально в Когоне дворец Бухары города внутри постройки на глазах, но Бухара на первый взгляд показалась религиоведам этому строгому сопротивлению, о котором они оказывали, в этом причина Религиоведы незнакомцы В Бухару препятствия на входе они делают Отсюда после дворца

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в 12 км к востоку от Бухары на участке «Новая Бухара», позже назовем его Когоном, в городе началось строительство около единственной остановки, о которой они договорились о данных, сделанных.

Ключевые слова: Амир, дворец Когонов, Мавритания в стиле барокко¹, эмпирический и арабский методы, Бенуа.

Bukhara of the emir In Kogon the palace about Bukhara of the emir In Kogon Palace XX century in their heads to Turkestan Russian of the emperor visit relationship with Syed Abd -ad- Akhad to the command mainly Russian and Bukhara masters by built.

The first on February 26, 1888 train Bukhara to the territory come in came. Iron of the road come in arrival , first of all , kybors category for big to happiness reason it has been . Bukhara amir Sayyid It is a price A bdulahadkhan during the years 1885-1910 Petersburg , Moscow and Crimea to their cities own family , officials with a lot there is a walk did Amir Yalta , Kislovodsk , Pyatigorsk , Zheleznovodsk such as spa in cities the most precious , mineral rich in water take a place in the land and settle down restore started That's it including A mir in 1894 A bdulahadkhan own both in the territory and abroad coming the guests worthy way waiting get in order to residence to build covenant does Own residence to build idea amir 1892 is close to A bdulahadkhan people with Russia cities across next to travel came out times peace does not give Caucasus , Petersburg , Moscow , Kiev , Yalta, Bogchasaroy , Tbilisi in cities is there Russian nobles luxurious life with met amir all to amenities have was national and European style wonderful building set up to reach decree will give .

Initially the palace Bukhara of the city inside construction in the eye will be held , but of Bukhara to the eye appeared religious scholars to this strictly resistance they show . The reason is religious scholars strangers To Bukhara entrances obstruction they do From this after the palace 12 km east of Bukhara in the section " New Bukhara " , later Call it Kogon started in the town construction about the only one stop they come Palace construction A mir A bdulahadkhan own of the era skillful architect Leontius Nikolaevich to Benoit believing submits From there almost 2 years time after Benoit the palace the project work out amir To A bdulahad Khan shows . In the project the guests waiting get for need will be all amenities in the eye caught were : hotels , restaurants , recreation rooms , bedrooms , bathrooms

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, luxurious waiting halls , recreation on the 2nd floor release for special porches of Benoit in the project each bilaterally thorough thought was Standing it's a project to the emir ok will be and the palace construction starting from is sent .

Sitarai Mohi Property Bukhara amir palace Palace construction began in 1895 and it is Mauritania in the style of baroque¹, empiric and Arabic methods harmonized without Bukhara and Russian skillful masters in the presence of set up will be done . Palace in decorations basically how much used is , har one room to himself typical way , high skill with decorated Building internal and external part one different , very even complicated location and to structure have construction in their work skillful an engineer Dubrovin leadership did Countless columns , large domes and towers the palace more glorious and majestic by doing shows .

Palace rooms from ganch processed Holland in style built ovens using heated . Ovens the only one in the scheme worked , that is room walls The term " Baroque " comes from the Italian word for " strange ", " extravagance ". inclined ” (defective pearl) . meanings means the center Italy XVII -XVIII centuries Europe culture feature is considered Baroque 16th century style the end of the 17th century in their heads last update during Rome, Italy Mantua Venice , Florence in cities appear was Baroque the period " West of civilization ” higher peak counted .

Empire is an empire method — architecture and practical in art last high classicism method . This method The reign of Emperor Napoleon I in France during appear 19th century initial three ten anniversary during developed and eclectic currents with exchanged across the air easily rotation for open corridors system conducted from ovens coming out heat never how to the fence without meeting room on the walls here it is that's it corridors through whole to the building rooms spread out heat with provided . Same that's it the wall between corridors through summer in season 3 meters of the building to the depth have basement part hole opened , in the basement cool the air whole the palace rooms across directed . So by doing Benoit of the project this thank you deserves part using the palace rooms in winter Hot and summer in season cool temperature with regularly respectively provided stood up

Palace right angular in the design longitudinal bullet across stretched large of halls from one to the other will be passed . Tarh in the center the most big hall located A mir during different kind of big from meetings from , to parties this in the hall held . Of the hall on the walls emboss in the form of ornaments from ganch skillfully

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by doing processed . Seven Holland ovens room for the sake of it good adding beauty more increased This big floor and ceiling of the hall replaced to be despite , on the wall emboss hanchkori ornaments original the carpet saved . Har one room on the walls type floral of decorations oriental soul lightning hit is standing

of the building second to the floor compact circulation the staircase using will be released , to their rooms while tanner arches with decorated open porches through will be passed . Second of the floor porch in the part The Qur'an from the book verses Arabic in the alphabet hanchkori ornaments with flower garden by doing finished Same so records of the building western on the side access the door on built porch in the columns Also , wood carving art using ornaments giving that it is written to see can Third from the floor basically necessary cases safety in order to used . Palace western from the door very charming national in style ornaments with flower garden by doing decorated to the room is entered . This is the room emirate during lobby task did it and here it is one century more time to the past despite on the walls skillfully drawn pattern niggers still own shine lost no . Person his eyes like dazzling just yesterday drawing such as lightning hit is standing of the room eastern on the wall Holland in style oven built , western the wall little arcuate into two layered windows (stained glass) are installed .

To the palace total three the door through entered all three of the building three on the side located skillful an architect Benoit building the project like that skill with work went to the palace one from the door entered person whole the palace absolutely another the door through output can.

Later on this from the palace Mangits of the dynasty last representative of Abdullah Khan son A mir Syed Olim Khan even To Bukhara came high official Guests for residence as used.

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